

French Modern Cities

Abstract

1920-1940:

facing the conventional urban development some experiences prepare the future:

- municipalist and SFU (French Society of Urbanists) urbanism;
- social housing in Paris: the red bricks wall of H. B. M. in Paris and the dutch influency;
- garden-cities in the suburbs: between english garden-cities and german-siedlungen;
- modero groups ofbuilding from Le Corbusier (Pessac, near Bordeaux), Mallet Stevens (in Paris) and others...

1940-1955:

war, damage and re-building: the birth of french state urban policy:

- the idea of planing towns and territolles;
- tradicional versus modero: the debate of the french reconstruction (Saint-Malo, Le Havre);
- Charta of Athens as state doctrine;
- first modero buildings in Marseille (Le Corbusier), Strasbourg (Beaudouin) ou Le Havre (Perret).

1955-1970:

from the rationalism ofbuilding process to the french «Grands Ensembles» (large social estates):

- Sarcelles and the «Caisse des Dépôts»
- Massy and the composite conception :
- Toulouse-Le Mirail and the french Team ten :
- Grenoble-la ville neuve and the french brutalism.

1965-1982:

apogy and decadency of the french centralicism:

- the '65 « schéma directeur » and the news towns «à la française »;
- Paris-ta Défense : a state project during half-century;
- the «Plan de Sauvegarde du Marais» and the

preservation policy;

-urban renovation.

1980-2000:

new direction in french urbanism:

- ZAC (concerted planning areas) between new haussmanism and new modernism;
- the question of peripheries;
- new centralities in the large town.

KEYWORDS

France, conventional urban development, re-building after war, rationalism, Grands Ensembles, new directions

Philippe Panerai was born in the Atlantic seashore of France in 1940. As a professor; since 1969, he conduced many rechearches and wrote books linked by urban problematics, such as "Formes urbaines, de l'ilot à la barre". As an urbanist, he is nowadays mainly working on the re-creation of urban fabrics in the "grands ensembles" in Grenoble and Sarcelles, on the constitution of the peripheric territory of cities, on the construction of public spaces in town.